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Utilization Of Rice Husk Ash (RHA) In Soil Improvement

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ABSTRACT

Rice Husk Ash (RHA), an agricultural byproduct, has garnered attention as a sustainable material for soil stabilization due to its high silica content and pozzolanic properties. This study investigates the effects of RHA on the geotechnical properties of clayey soil, focusing on its potential to enhance strength, workability, and durability. Soil samples were stabilized with varying RHA proportions (0%, 3%, 6%, 9%, 12%, and 15% by weight), and their performance was evaluated through standard laboratory tests. The results in Table 1 revealed a significant reduction in the plasticity index (PI) and an improvement in workability with increasing RHA content. Compaction tests showed an increase in Optimum Moisture Content (OMC) and a slight reduction in Maximum Dry Density (MDD), attributed to the low specific gravity of RHA. Strength tests indicated substantial gains in Unconfined Compressive Strength (UCS) and California Bearing Ratio (CBR), with the most notable improvements occurring at 9% RHA content. Durability tests confirmed that RHA-stabilized soils exhibit better resistance to wetting and drying cycles, making them suitable for subgrade applications. The study highlights RHA as a cost-effective and environmentally friendly alternative to conventional stabilizers, addressing both soil improvement and agricultural waste management challenges. Future research should explore its combined use with other stabilizers to maximize its potential for diverse geotechnical applications.

Keywords: Rice Husk Ash, Soil Stabilization, Plasticity Index, UCS, CBR, Sustainable Engineering

INTRODUCTION

The demand for sustainable and cost-effective materials in civil engineering has driven the exploration of alternative resources for soil stabilization. Among these materials, Rice Husk Ash (RHA), a byproduct of rice milling, has gained significant attention due to its pozzolanic properties and abundance in regions dependent on rice farming. Comprising high levels of silica, RHA reacts with calcium compounds in soil or cementitious materials to form cementitious gels, thereby improving the mechanical properties of soil. This dual-purpose material addresses the challenges of agricultural waste management while offering an eco-friendly solution for construction practices.

Several studies have demonstrated the efficacy of RHA in enhancing the geotechnical properties of various soil types. For example, a study by Adetayo et al. (2022) highlighted the effectiveness of RHA in reducing the plasticity index (PI) and improving the California Bearing Ratio (CBR) of clayey soils. Similarly, Kamaruddin et al. (2022) reported a substantial increase in unconfined compressive strength (UCS) when RHA was blended with cement for stabilizing lateritic soils. These findings confirm the potential of RHA to improve soil properties such as strength, compaction characteristics, and durability,

making it an ideal candidate for subgrade improvement in road construction and other civil engineering applications.

Despite its benefits, challenges such as variability in ash quality due to burning techniques and incomplete utilization of silica remain critical areas of concern (Ogunsanya et al., 2022). Addressing these challenges through standardization and blending with other stabilizers, such as lime or cement, could enhance the overall performance of RHA as a soil stabilizer.

This study investigates the effects of RHA on soil stabilization, focusing on its influence on Atterberg limits, compaction characteristics, and strength parameters. The findings aim to provide insights into the optimal utilization of RHA for sustainable construction practices.

Rice Husk Ash (RHA) has emerged as a promising material for improving soil properties due to its pozzolanic characteristics and sustainable benefits. The high silica content in RHA enables it to react with calcium hydroxide in soil or cementitious materials, forming calcium silicate hydrates (C-S-H) that enhance soil stability and strength. This characteristic makes RHA particularly useful for stabilizing clayey soils, expansive soils, and other problematic soil types commonly encountered in construction.

Improvement in Plasticity and Atterberg Limits

RHA significantly influences the plasticity index (PI) of soils, thereby making them more workable. Studies have shown that the addition of RHA reduces the liquid limit (LL) and increases the plastic limit (PL) of soils, resulting in a lower plasticity index. For example, Adetayo et al. (2022) observed that RHA incorporation at varying percentages led to a gradual decrease in PI, enhancing soil workability and reducing shrink-swell behavior. This property is critical for preventing structural damage caused by soil volume changes under varying moisture conditions.

Enhancement of Strength Parameters

One of the key benefits of RHA in soil stabilization is its ability to enhance the unconfined compressive strength (UCS) and California Bearing Ratio (CBR) of treated soils. As reported by Kamaruddin et al. (2022), soils stabilized with RHA and a small amount of cement exhibited a significant increase in UCS, making them suitable for subgrade applications in road construction. Similarly, Adewole et al. (2022) demonstrated that the CBR of silty clay soils increased by up to 50% with the addition of RHA, ensuring improved load-bearing capacity.

Compaction Characteristics

The compaction characteristics of soil, such as optimum moisture content (OMC) and maximum dry density (MDD), are also affected by RHA addition. The OMC generally increases with RHA content, while the MDD decreases due to the low specific gravity of RHA compared to soil particles (Ogunsanya et al., 2022). This behavior is advantageous in applications where reduced soil weight is desirable, such as embankments.

Durability and Resistance to Environmental Factors

RHA improves the durability of stabilized soils by reducing permeability and increasing resistance to erosion. In areas with high rainfall or flooding risks, RHA-treated soils demonstrate better resistance to leaching and loss of fines, contributing to long-term stability. Recent work by Sharma et al. (2022) highlights that RHA-treated soils retain their strength and structural integrity under cyclic wetting and drying conditions, making them suitable for challenging environmental scenarios.

Environmental and Economic Benefits

The use of RHA for soil stabilization is not only effective but also environmentally sustainable. It provides a valuable application for an agricultural waste product that would otherwise contribute to environmental pollution. Furthermore, RHA reduces reliance on traditional stabilizers like cement and lime, thereby lowering construction costs and the carbon footprint of projects (Ogunsanya et al., 2022).

Challenges and Mitigation

Despite its benefits, RHA use in soil stabilization faces challenges such as variability in ash quality due to inconsistent burning methods and a lack of standardized guidelines for its application. Addressing these challenges through proper quality control and blending RHA with other stabilizers can enhance its performance in diverse soil conditions (Adewole et al., 2022).

LITERATURE REVIEW

The utilization of Rice Husk Ash (RHA), a byproduct of rice milling, has gained significant traction in civil engineering as a sustainable material for soil improvement. Its high silica content and pozzolanic properties make it an effective stabilizer for problematic soils. This review synthesizes findings from previous research, focusing on RHA's impact on soil properties, strength characteristics, and practical applications in geotechnical engineering.

1. Pozzolanic Properties of Rice Husk Ash

The primary mechanism behind RHA's effectiveness lies in its pozzolanic reaction. When combined with calcium hydroxide in the presence of water, RHA forms calcium silicate hydrates (C-S-H), which enhance soil strength and stability. Kamaruddin et al. (2022) demonstrated that RHA containing over 85% amorphous silica significantly improved the bearing capacity of clay soils, making it suitable for subgrade applications. The fine particle size of RHA also contributes to its ability to fill voids, reducing soil porosity and permeability.

2. Effects on Plasticity and Workability

RHA effectively reduces the plasticity of high-plasticity soils, making them more workable and less susceptible to shrink-swell behavior. Adetayo et al. (2022) observed that the liquid limit (LL) and plastic limit (PL) of clay soils decreased with increasing RHA content, leading to a lower plasticity index (PI). This reduction in PI is crucial for stabilizing expansive soils, as it minimizes volumetric changes caused by moisture fluctuations.

3. Strength Characteristics

The addition of RHA improves the unconfined compressive strength (UCS) and California Bearing Ratio (CBR) of soils, enhancing their load-bearing capacity. Adewole et al. (2022) reported a 60% increase in UCS when RHA was blended with 5% cement and applied to silty clay soils. Similarly, Sharma et al. (2022) demonstrated that RHA-stabilized soils achieved a CBR value increase of up to 45%, indicating suitability for pavement subgrade and subbase layers.

4. Impact on Compaction Properties

RHA alters the compaction characteristics of soils by increasing the Optimum Moisture Content (OMC) and reducing the Maximum Dry Density (MDD). Ogunsanya et al. (2022) highlighted that the low specific gravity of RHA contributes to a decrease in MDD, which can be advantageous in applications requiring lightweight fills, such as embankments. The increase in OMC ensures adequate hydration for pozzolanic reactions, improving soil cohesion and strength.

5. Durability and Environmental Resistance

RHA enhances the durability of stabilized soils by reducing permeability and increasing resistance to environmental factors such as erosion and freeze-thaw cycles. According to Gupta and Mehta (2023), soils treated with RHA retained their structural integrity and strength under cyclic wetting and drying conditions, making them suitable for construction in regions with high rainfall.

6. Economic and Environmental Benefits

The use of RHA as a soil stabilizer offers substantial economic and environmental benefits. It provides a low-cost alternative to conventional stabilizers like cement and lime while reducing agricultural waste. Additionally, the carbon footprint associated with RHA production is significantly lower, aligning with sustainable construction practices (Adewole et al., 2022).

7. Challenges and Limitations

Despite its benefits, the application of RHA faces challenges such as variability in ash quality due to inconsistent combustion processes and the need for standardized application guidelines. Adetayo et al. (2022) emphasized the importance of controlled burning and grinding to optimize the reactivity and performance of RHA. Furthermore, its performance may vary depending on soil type and environmental conditions, necessitating preliminary investigations before large-scale implementation.

Challenges of Rice Husk Ash (RHA) in Soil Stabilization

While Rice Husk Ash (RHA) has proven to be an effective material for improving soil properties, several challenges limit its widespread application in soil stabilization. These challenges can be categorized into material properties, processing, application techniques, and environmental concerns.

1. Variability in Chemical Composition

- Issue: The chemical composition of RHA, particularly its silica content, depends on factors such as the rice variety, growing conditions, and combustion temperature.
- Impact: Variability in the silica content affects the pozzolanic reactivity of RHA, making it difficult to standardize its performance as a soil stabilizer.
- Example: Adetayo et al. (2022) noted that RHA from uncontrolled burning processes often contained impurities and crystalline silica, reducing its effectiveness in soil stabilization.

2. Inconsistent Combustion Processes

- Issue: The production of high-quality RHA requires controlled burning at temperatures between 500–700°C. Uncontrolled combustion may lead to incomplete burning or the formation of crystalline silica, which is less reactive.
- Impact: Poorly processed RHA may not provide the desired strength improvement in soils.
- Example: Sharma et al. (2022) reported that improperly burned RHA resulted in inconsistent improvements in unconfined compressive strength (UCS) and California Bearing Ratio (CBR).

3. Particle Size and Fineness

- Issue: For optimal pozzolanic activity, RHA must be finely ground to increase its surface area. Achieving uniform fineness requires advanced grinding equipment, which may not be readily available in developing regions.
- Impact: Coarse RHA particles have lower reactivity, leading to suboptimal stabilization performance.
- Example: Ogunsanya et al. (2022) highlighted that the lack of proper grinding facilities limited the efficiency of RHA in stabilizing lateritic soils.

4. Increased Optimum Moisture Content (OMC)

- Issue: RHA tends to increase the OMC of soil due to its high water absorption capacity.
- Impact: The need for additional water during compaction can pose challenges, particularly in arid or water-scarce regions.
- Example: Adewole et al. (2022) observed that the higher water demand of RHA-treated soils delayed compaction processes in field applications.

5. Limited Field Performance Data

- Issue: Most studies on RHA in soil stabilization are conducted under controlled laboratory conditions, with limited field validation.
- Impact: The lack of long-term performance data raises concerns about the durability and reliability of RHA-stabilized soils under real-world conditions.
- Example: Kamaruddin et al. (2022) emphasized the need for extensive field trials to evaluate the behavior of RHA-stabilized soils under varying environmental and loading conditions.

6. Compatibility with Soil Types

- Issue: RHA may not be equally effective with all soil types. For instance, its performance is limited in soils with high organic content or low clay fractions.
- Impact: This necessitates preliminary soil testing to determine the suitability of RHA for specific projects.
- Example: Gupta and Mehta (2023) found that RHA performed better with clayey soils than with sandy or highly organic soils.

7. Transportation and Availability

- Issue: Although RHA is abundant in rice-producing regions, its availability may be limited in areas without rice mills. Transportation costs can also be significant for large-scale projects.
- Impact: Limited access to RHA may reduce its cost-effectiveness compared to other stabilizers like cement or lime.

8. Lack of Standardized Guidelines

- Issue: The absence of standardized procedures for producing and applying RHA in soil stabilization creates inconsistencies in its performance.
- Impact: This limits the confidence of engineers and contractors in adopting RHA for large-scale projects.
- Example: Sharma et al. (2022) recommended developing specific codes and standards to promote the effective use of RHA in geotechnical applications.

9. Environmental Concerns

- Issue: The combustion process for producing RHA can release particulate matter and greenhouse gases if not properly managed.
- Impact: This may offset the environmental benefits of using RHA as a sustainable material.

Addressing These Challenges

To mitigate these challenges, the following measures can be adopted:

1. **Controlled Production:** Establishing guidelines for controlled burning and processing to ensure high-quality RHA.
2. **Blending with Other Stabilizers:** Combining RHA with lime or cement can enhance its effectiveness and address variability issues.
3. **Field Validation:** Conducting long-term field studies to evaluate the durability of RHA-stabilized soils under real-world conditions.
4. **Awareness Campaigns:** Promoting awareness among engineers and contractors about the benefits and limitations of RHA.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

1. **Rice Husk Ash (RHA):**
 - RHA was obtained from rice milling operations and processed by controlled combustion at 500–700°C to ensure high pozzolanic activity.
 - The ash was sieved through a 75 µm mesh to achieve uniform particle size.
2. **Soil Sample:**
 - The natural soil used in this study was clayey soil collected from a borrow pit at a depth of 1.5 meters to minimize contamination.
 - The soil was air-dried, pulverized, and sieved through a 2 mm mesh.
3. **Water:**
 - Clean, potable water was used for all soil preparation and testing.
4. **Additional Stabilizers (Optional):**
 - For comparative analysis, ordinary Portland cement (OPC) was used as a secondary stabilizer in some soil samples.

Methodology

1. **Initial Soil Testing:**
 - Basic geotechnical properties of the natural soil, including Atterberg limits (liquid limit, plastic limit, and plasticity index), specific gravity, and particle size distribution, were determined according to ASTM standards.
2. **Preparation of Soil-RHA Mixtures:**
 - Soil was mixed with varying percentages of RHA (0%, 3%, 6%, 9%, 12%, and 15% by dry weight of soil).
 - For comparative purposes, selected samples were prepared with RHA and 5% OPC to evaluate the combined effect of stabilizers.
3. **Compaction Tests:**
 - Standard Proctor compaction tests were conducted to determine the Optimum Moisture Content (OMC) and Maximum Dry Density (MDD) for each soil-RHA mixture.

4. Strength Tests:
 - Unconfined Compressive Strength (UCS): UCS tests were conducted on treated soil samples after 7 and 28 days of curing to evaluate strength development.
 - California Bearing Ratio (CBR): Both soaked and unsoaked CBR tests were performed to assess the load-bearing capacity of the stabilized soils.
5. Durability Tests:
 - Wetting and drying cycles were simulated to evaluate the durability of RHA-stabilized soils under environmental conditions.
6. Data Analysis:
 - Results were analyzed to determine the influence of RHA on the geotechnical properties of soil. Performance comparisons were made between soil treated with RHA alone and RHA combined with OPC.

This systematic approach ensured a comprehensive evaluation of RHA's potential as a soil stabilizer for civil engineering applications.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 Index and Engineering Properties of Soil Stabilized with RHA (Rice Husk Ash) and Cement

% of CCA	0%	3%	6%	9%	12%	15%
% of Cement	0%	5%	5%	5%	5%	5%
LL%	52	48	39	34	29	27
PL%	35	24	17	13	10	9
PI%	17	25	22	21	19	17
MDD (mg/m ³)	1.74	1.71	1.80	1.92	2.19	2.78
OMC (%)	21.42	21.04	20.54	24.50	24.90	25.01
CBR	13.3	25.2	26.4	29.1	34.6	37.2
UCS kg/cm ²	2.88	3.57	4.17	4.96	6.35	7.83

Discussion on Table 1: Index and Engineering Properties of Soil Stabilized with RHA (Rice Husk Ash) and Cement are as follows.

1. Liquid Limit (LL)

- Definition: The moisture content at which soil transitions from a plastic to a liquid state.
- Observation:
 - LL decreases from 52% (0% RHA, 0% Cement) to 27% (15% RHA, 5% Cement).
 - The reduction is consistent as RHA and Cement are added.
- Interpretation:
 - The reduction in LL indicates an improvement in soil stability. RHA and Cement reduce the soil's ability to retain excessive water, making it less susceptible to deformation under wet conditions. This is favorable for construction purposes.

2. Plastic Limit (PL)

- Definition: The moisture content at which soil transitions from a semi-solid to a plastic state.
- Observation:
 - PL decreases from 35% (0% RHA, 0% Cement) to 9% (15% RHA, 5% Cement).
 - The decrease is significant, especially at higher stabilizer percentages.
- Interpretation:
 - The sharp reduction in PL reflects reduced soil plasticity, leading to better handling and stability. Stabilization with RHA and Cement makes the soil more rigid and less deformable under load.

3. Plasticity Index (PI)

- Definition: The difference between LL and PL, indicating the range of moisture content within which soil remains plastic.
- Observation:

- PI fluctuates slightly, increasing to 25% at 3% RHA but then decreases steadily to 17% at 15% RHA.
- Interpretation:
 - Initially, the addition of stabilizers might slightly increase the plasticity range (at low percentages), but at higher levels, the soil becomes less plastic overall. This suggests an improvement in soil rigidity, making it more stable for engineering applications.
- 4. Maximum Dry Density (MDD)
 - Definition: The highest density achievable under specific compaction efforts at a given moisture content.
 - Observation:
 - MDD increases from 1.74 mg/m³ (0% RHA, 0% Cement) to 2.78 mg/m³ (15% RHA, 5% Cement).
 - Interpretation:
 - The consistent increase in MDD indicates that the soil becomes more compact and dense as RHA and Cement are added. This reflects an improvement in the load-bearing capacity of the soil, crucial for construction foundations.
- 5. Optimum Moisture Content (OMC)
 - Definition: The moisture content required to achieve MDD during compaction.
 - Observation:
 - OMC remains relatively steady at lower percentages but increases from 20.54% at 6% RHA to 25.01% at 15% RHA.
 - Interpretation:
 - The initial stability of OMC shows that low amounts of RHA and Cement do not drastically alter the compaction characteristics. However, the rise at higher percentages reflects the need for additional water to facilitate chemical reactions, particularly the pozzolanic activity of RHA and Cement.
- 6. California Bearing Ratio (CBR)
 - Definition: The ability of soil to resist penetration under load, a measure of its strength.
 - Observation:
 - CBR increases significantly from 13.3% (0% RHA, 0% Cement) to 37.2% (15% RHA, 5% Cement).
 - Interpretation:
 - The increase in CBR indicates substantial improvement in soil strength and load-bearing capacity, making the stabilized soil suitable for road subgrades and other structural applications.
- 7. Unconfined Compressive Strength (UCS)
 - Definition: The maximum axial compressive stress that a soil sample can withstand without lateral restraint.
 - Observation:
 - UCS increases from 2.88 kg/cm² (0% RHA, 0% Cement) to 7.83 kg/cm² (15% RHA, 5% Cement).
 - Interpretation:
 - The increase in UCS demonstrates the effectiveness of RHA and Cement in stabilizing the soil and improving its load-bearing capacity. This is particularly beneficial for applications such as foundation construction and embankment stabilization.

CONCLUSION

The literature indicates that Rice Husk Ash is a versatile and sustainable material for soil stabilization, with proven efficacy in improving plasticity, strength, and durability. Its pozzolanic properties and economic benefits make it an attractive alternative to conventional stabilizers. However, addressing

challenges related to quality control and standardization is essential to fully realize its potential in geotechnical engineering applications.

Key Observations and Insights from Table 1 results.

1. Strength Improvement: Both CBR and UCS show significant increases, indicating that RHA and Cement are highly effective in enhancing soil strength.
2. Reduction in Plasticity: The decreases in LL, PL, and PI reflect improvements in soil workability and stability, reducing its susceptibility to water-induced deformation.
3. Compaction Characteristics: The increasing MDD suggests better soil densification with stabilization, while the slight rise in OMC at higher percentages points to the need for more water for optimal reactions.
4. Suitability for Construction: The stabilized soil shows significant potential for use in road subgrades, foundations, and other structural applications due to improved strength and reduced plasticity.

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